

The Travails of the Living Dead Child Bride

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Child marriage is a social evil that still haunts the lives of many girls in our country. This paper takes into account the various factors that can mar a girl's life owing to child marriage. The ordeal of child marriage results in a loss of agency that a girl has over her body, her dreams and aspirations, decision-making power, socialization, access to health care, her appearance, and even the perceptions about her. Thus, the unfortunate occurrence of her marriage undermines her total self-esteem. A review of the literature showed that the majority of the studies neglect the personality aspect while studying the grave consequences of child marriage. This paper, therefore, tries to highlight the personality aspects too. Patriarchy being at the root of the deeply entrenched societal norms that thwart gender parity is examined closely. Poverty, lack of education, and ignorance that propels child marriage are discussed here as well. It also looks at how the pandemic has enhanced her vulnerabilities manifold.

Introduction

Child marriage is a global concern and is rooted in societal norms and practices, springing from patriarchy. The multitude of factors that fuel it is entrenched poverty, poor education and gender inequality. At the global level, 12 million girls are married before the age of 18 every year. As per the UNICEF Child Marriage Database, 2020, this amounts to 23 girls every minute and nearly 1 every 3 seconds (Travers, 2018). These figures are numbing for any sane person. Child marriage is therefore increasingly viewed as a violation of basic human rights and child rights, having far-reaching implications on the personalities of children and adolescents especially in terms of access to opportunities; as well as survival and development (Paul, 2019; Shawki, 2015; Wodon, 2015). However, to this day, it shockingly remains a deeply entrenched practice, and is hence stark evidence of rampant gender inequality and discrimination.

The problem of child marriage in India is a sociological phenomenon with extensive historical evidence of men's structural domination over women. This unequal status of women stems from the patriarchal control over their sexuality, the socio-economic inequalities, deprivation of education

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and subsequent livelihood, and suppressing the agency of women at all levels (Charlesworth, et al., 1991; Marphatia, et al., 2017; Osthus & Sewpaul, 2014). The structural constraints are palpable in the skewed sex ratios and other developmental markers such as health, education, employment, social and economic mobility, and leisure time for girls and women. All these illustrate women's lower status in Indian society.

Adolescence represents a very crucial stage of transition from childhood to adulthood. Socio-economic, biological, and demographic events during this phase have implications on their future lives, which in turn has implications for the country's future. It is therefore paramount that adolescents transition through this with their rights being protected, their needs and vulnerabilities addressed, and with adequate opportunities for growth and development. However, far from being a time of innocence, pleasure and freedom, childhood for the child bride is filled with darkness, danger, pain, and trauma (Hasday, 2000). When a girl is married, her childhood is robbed; and she is denied of a world that a girl of her age should ideally experience.

Gender norms become more apparent and formalized during adolescence. Increased restrictions make an adolescent girl vulnerable to various forms of exploitation and discrimination both within and outside the family. Studies have revealed that girls, especially from marginalized communities have high rates of illiteracy, forced marriages, resulting in early and unintended pregnancies. Child marriage is one such harrowing event that maims the child for life in all aspects. Patriarchy, gendered ideals of decision making and blind faith in orthodox rituals promote child marriage in society. The 'chastity' of a girl is also considered paramount before marriage (Santhya, Haberland & Singh, 2006; Temin, et al, 2010; Psaki, 2016). These lop-sided social conditions also perpetuate ignorance and poverty. Gender parity remains elusive. Such socio-cultural, economic and geographical determinants thus place adolescents, especially girls in a vulnerable and exploitative situation.

The Indian Context

Around 41 per cent of India's population is below 20 years of age (Census 2011). It also enumerates approximately 253 million adolescents in India comprising slightly more than one-fifth of India's population. Data also reveals that in India, adolescent girls in the age group of 10-19 are more vulnerable to increased instances of school dropout, early marriage, early

pregnancy as well as harassment and violence. The pandemic has only worsened it.

NHFS-4 (2015-2016) revealed that the prevalence of child marriage amongst girls in India of 15-19 years is 11.9 per cent and 26.8 per cent for those between 20-24 years. 14.1 per cent in rural and 6.9 per cent girls in urban areas were already married in the age group of 15-19 years. It was 31.5 per cent in rural and 17.5 per cent in urban areas the age group of 20-24 years. 7.9 per cent of women aged between 15-19 years were already mothers or were pregnant. Poverty and minimal or even complete absence of education characterised these households where child marriage was rampant. Thus, data shows the pervasiveness of child marriage in our country. The complexities of traditions and customs, poverty, and entrenched orthodox practices prove to be fertile grounds for child marriage to remain ingrained. The child bride, on the other hand, is physically and emotionally scarred for life, thus affecting her personality.

The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006, renders child marriage illegal in India but the practice continues unabated, particularly in economically disadvantaged communities. Ironically, UNICEF reported that in 2007-2008, as many as 42.9 per cent of the married women surveyed in the age group 20-24 years were married before eighteen. The legislation did not deter India from contributing as many as 40 per cent of the world's child brides (Abbi, et al., 2013).

Child marriage has been a practice in India for centuries and is traced back to ancient times. Some scholars state that the practice set in during the medieval period. No doubt marriages were occurring at an early age especially for girls; which were then more commonly referred to as early marriages. Samita Sen (2021) notes that the term "*balyavivaha*", which is a translation of child marriage, came into wider use in the wake of the social reform movements. She adds that the term acquired more room for debate at the beginning of the nineteenth century, regarding the practice of *sati* (self-immolation on the funeral pyre of the husband). There was a lot of disconcertment regarding whether a child widow should commit *sati*. The haunting image of the child widow also added to the controversy of child marriage. By the turn of the nineteenth century, nearly a quarter of women in Bengal were widows. Hence the tide began turning against early/ child marriages gradually.

These young child brides have womanhood thrust on them perforce and they endure undeniable misery but most of its impact remains obscure. In the Indian context, the union of marriage is placed on a high

pedestal and acquires a sense of sacredness and it is supposed to usher in profound joy to the uniting families. It strengthens kinship ties and promotes social and economic obligations. Traditional norms and values bind the relation. This cannot be said about child marriage though. The intricately woven socio-economic and cultural factors egged on by a patriarchal society, and poor implementation of laws, give leeway for child marriage to persist. Several factors are responsible for the continuation of this reprehensible practise which has resulted in a situation where the girl child's life is rendered hollow and scarred. Some of them are discussed in the ensuing paragraphs.

Woman's Agency

Simone de Beauvoir (1953) in her revolutionary book, 'The Second Sex' points out that the way in which a young girl who goes on to become a woman experiences her body is determined by others' 'gaze' and how she internalizes it. This is a sorrowful mirage where society determines what must a woman undergo or be perceived as; and not by the woman herself (Collins, 1986; Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). Considering the compulsive social forces that a young girl is subjected to, it is evident that these girls who are married at a young age end up in a vulnerable position. During adolescence, a girl goes through a lot of changes which has implications not only for her body, but also on her mental health, and overall personality. Being such a sensitive and significant point in their lives, it is important that they pass this stage with their needs met and their rights upheld. Child marriage snatches away these opportunities for a lifetime.

These young married girls also neither have any say in terms of sexual relations nor in reproductive issues, which can affect both their physical and mental health. Sex is often forced by their respective partners despite their reluctance; the reasons being fear, illness, tiredness, occupancy with other household chores etc. These forceful acts prevent them from discovering their bodies at their own pace as they are pushed into sexual relations by their partners (Gagnon, 1965; Feder, et al., 2006). Such unnerving experiences many times result in them being scared of the marital relationship and thereby they suffer from other health as well as anxiety-related problems; all of which affect their overall personalities. Marion (2010) argues that patriarchy manifests itself in many forms and is mainly responsible for creating cultural values in favour of child marriages. It is equally accountable for promoting gender norms that support male dominance in sexual relations.

Marriage itself does not easily recognize forced sex as an offence. There is no legal right available to wives to say ‘No’ or ‘Yes’. Sec 375 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) defines ‘rape’ to include all forms of sexual assault involving non-consensual intercourse with a woman. However, exception 2 to the section renders the husband immune from prosecution. Non-consensual sexual intercourse between spouses is not ‘rape’ if the wife is above 15 years of age. Current law entails that a wife is presumed to mandatorily consent for sex with her husband (Makkar, 2019). Herein lies another catch as the legal age at marriage is stated as 18 for a girl. Such contradicting provisions that are biased towards men make implementing the legislation even more difficult. India Today Web Desk (2016) reported that out of the thirty-six countries that still have not criminalized marital rape, India is one of them. The courts of India including the Supreme Court are overwhelmed with writ petitions challenging this exception. Consequently, in a landmark judgement, the Supreme Court (2017) criminalized unwilling sexual contact with a wife between 15 and 18 years of age. This is the beginning. Many more writ petitions have thus followed, challenging this exception to Sec 375 on the premise that it violates Article 14 (equality before the law) and Article 21 (protection of life and personal liberty) of the Constitution.

The position of young wives is more vulnerable compared to that of older adult wives. The awareness about protective legal mechanisms is a far-fetched reality for the child brides, as such brides belong mostly to the deprived and marginalised sections and are bereft of education too. The sex taboo in Indian society, especially in a rural society, worsens things. It prevents them from being informed about the topic. Sex and puberty are considered to be embarrassing, distasteful, and dirty subjects; not to be discussed. Girls are not given any sex education by anyone after they attain menarche and hence remain ill aware of what can unfold in their bodies, and their lives after adolescence and marriage (Johnston, 1993; Brain, et al., 1977; Shah, 2011).

The Sex Taboo

The secrecy that envelops all discussions about the ‘body’ and more so, the female body, is a prime factor that society must address in battling various social evils; with child marriage being one of them. In a scenario where discussions around sex, even in the context of marital relations are hushed up, schools can play an important role. The irony however is that teachers themselves consider it a taboo. Moreover, the presence of more male teachers in the education system acts as a disincentive for discussions. The system itself is also hesitant about imparting sex education (Chowdhury, 2020).

Child marriage indeed is a severe form of child abuse. Hence inculcating sex education at the school level can give good leverage in the right direction.

India has an adolescent population of 243 million; with more than 50 per cent of them in urban areas. Delivering sex education in a timely manner will help improve their general health conditions, nutritional status, and more importantly, their sexual and reproductive health. WHO has emphasized that primarily during adolescence (10-19 years), sex education provision is a crucial preventative tool because it is the time when these adolescents experience a range of physiological and behavioural changes. UNAIDS, UNICEF and the UNPF emphasize the effectiveness of sex education in various parts of the world, in promoting overall adolescent health for a healthy society. Likewise, India can benefit a lot by undoing the sex taboo via meaningful sex education (Ismail, et al., 2015).

The Magnified Vulnerabilities of the Child Bride

Newly married adolescents face extreme sexual vulnerabilities, as they are uninformed, and totally unprepared for sexual intercourse and its consequences. Overall, the apprehension of scorn and disdain from adults for showing curiosity in such issues frequently deter adolescents from any earnest efforts at overcoming their ignorance. For them, their peers remain an accessible source. Being adolescents and inexperienced themselves; the information provided is usually incorrect and incomplete. This puts the girls in a doubly vulnerable position (Abraham, 2001; Jejeebhoy & Bott, 2003). Ignorance coupled with misinformation places the young girls in jeopardy.

Parents thus prefer marrying their daughters during adolescence as the virginity and chastity of a girl go hand in hand. The patriarchal society attributes the family honour to it and virgins are accorded a high social value. The virginity of a girl is of immense significance before her marriage. Early marriage is therefore the all encumbering mechanism to ensure that the girl remains chaste and thus safeguard the honour of the family. Young girls are also preferred for marriage as they can be controlled easily. Social mores and norms, therefore, continue to deprive a woman of any agency of her own (Kapadia, 1966; Mohlakoana, 2008).

The Appearance of a Woman

The relationship between a woman and her body is a complex one. Women continuously receive instructions concerning how they should function, behave, and even appear. (Williams, 1984; Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; Wichstrom, 1999). These instructions come from different sources ranging from the society they live in, to the various forms of media. The woman's

body is projected to look and behave within an encapsulated framework set out by social norms. This is for a lifetime. It brings along disappointment, anxiety, as well as disempowerment. Social norm theories point out that people comply with the norms set for them under two circumstances. Firstly, when they value other people's approval even if they do not subscribe to the norm. Secondly, when they are scared of the negative reactions as a result of non-conformity. In Indian society, most married women confess that they are scared of the repercussions of not dressing in the prescribed manner thus impinging upon their freedom and choice of appearance (Thapan, 2004).

The adolescent girls being young, have little agency to go against the decisions made by the elders, especially men. Clothes are one of the many ways through which people express themselves. This form of expression is often not given to girls, and particularly to married women. Women and girls are supposed to be dressed in a certain way and if they dress differently, they are either accused of insulting society or inviting the attention of male members of the society. The attire of a woman is reflective and often a sign to other men that a particular woman is married and she must conduct herself appropriately. Christianson and others underline the feminine 'honour code' as those that conform to chastity, modesty, certain attire norms, and controlled social interactions with men (Christianson, et. al. 2021). This 'code' serves to determine the family's 'honour'.

Decision Making

In 1992, India ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of a Child. It establishes participation in decision making as a right of every adolescent as it can affect their lives. Major efforts are being made to promote it at the national and international levels. However, at the individual level, this aspect is often neglected. Married women also face more restrictions; especially in terms of their freedom to go alone. It may be to visit the natal family or even to access health care facilities (Rosenzweig & Stark, 1989; Kabeer, 2005, Luke & Munshi, 2011).

The NHFS-4 (2015-2016) findings of India highlights that 91 per cent of male members in the families participate in household decision making while only 16 per cent of the women do so. This highlights the sheer skewness of gender in decision making. Kopelman also (2016) emphasizes that early marriage deprives their decision-making capacities. No one pays heed to their emotions or aspirations. Rather a world of the dangers of teenage pregnancy and its accompanying traumas awaits them. Thus, the agency of a young woman and her personality development opportunities are robbed as she has to tread very carefully on the path carved out by society,

lest she brings ‘dishonour’ to her family. Given the burden that a young girl has to carry; and be the prophetic archetype on whom the family honour rests, it is rather a paradox that she cannot participate in decision making.

With regards to healthcare too, it is often found that the decision is taken by someone else. These young brides are usually dependent on their husbands and mothers-in law in terms of seeking healthcare, especially when the crucial birthing process is involved. A woman’s health is not taken seriously till the time she is no longer able to work, reflecting the casual attitude that the family members and society at large hold towards women. Mandal and others (2020) have also underlined in their study that women’s autonomy is very significant to determine access to maternity care in India.

Early Marriage and Poor Reproductive Health

Ravi Prakash and others examined NFHS data (2005-2006) to understand the effects of early marriage on women’s reproductive health as well as on the well-being of the children they bear. They concluded that early marriage was detrimental to the health status of both mother and child in terms of poor nutritional status, lower chances of survival, and stunting, wasting, being underweight etc. Loss of life of the young mother at childbirth is also a common occurrence (Prakash, et al., 2011). Besides these, there are also the dangers of acquiring HIV/ STDs as the male partner is in a position to negotiate his sexual preferences in most cases being older and experienced. Contrastingly, the young bride is in a vulnerable position owing to a lack of knowledge about safe sex and other contraceptive practices. Moreover, mere knowledge cannot withstand the eventuality of forceful non-consensual intercourse with their spouses. Keeping the urgency of the nature of the problem of early/ child marriage, WHO had addressed the issue at the sixty-fifth World Health Assembly in 2012. Thereafter, WHO policies such as Health 2020 have been envisioned which highlight the need for adequate protection of adolescents’ health and better research and surveillance so that it can be tackled more effectively (WHO, 2012).

Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is the value judgement that a person has about himself or herself. It gives us an insight into the self-worth of a person and the extent to which the person likes or values himself or herself. Self-esteem tends to have a strong relation to happiness. It can play an important role in an individual’s life especially in terms of motivation and success. In the hierarchy of needs, Abraham Maslow also talks about self-esteem as being one of the basic

human motivations and its importance towards reaching the last stage of self-actualization. However, extreme self-esteem levels at the higher or the lower ends are both harmful (Poduska, 1992; Taormina & Gao, 2013)

Low levels of self-esteem further hamper the motivation levels, which in turn has implications on the overall personality of the girl child. Several factors can be held responsible for the low levels of self-esteem among married girls. A society with its different notions and restrictions about the various aspects of a girl's life continue to lower her self-esteem. Unsupportive parents, in-laws, and husbands also contribute to low levels of self-esteem (Niaz & Hassan, 2006; Mahapatro & Singh, 2020; Bhattacharya, et al., 2019).

The fact that almost every aspect of a married girls' life is controlled or decided or negotiated by someone else is one of the prime causes of her low self-esteem. Motivation and happiness are severely affected as a result of a person not valuing and liking themselves which further hampers everything they do in life and hence their personalities too.

All About Being a Girl

A girl is still considered a burden by society and the practice of child marriage in the present times is one of the tragic outcomes of that thinking. Due to the various restrictions and the sacrifices that come along with the identity of being a girl, the majority of them are unhappy about being a girl. Rosaldo (1974) thus opines that often a 'good' girl is considered to perform various household chores diligently, not go out alone, being religious-minded, and being obedient and almost subservient. Girls are therefore expected to submit to the needs, demands and decisions of other people; whether of the family or relatives and society at large. Any girl who defies these societal norms is quickly labelled as 'bad'. Parents are often seen adopting these norms as a mark of demarcation between a good and a bad girl.

Historically, *Manusmriti* has also laid down guidelines for a 'good woman' as one who remains bound by the encumbrances of society and refrains from satiating all her physical and sensual urges. Never faltering to appease her husband heightens her virtuosity and she would attain the 'higher' world of her husband in the next (Larson, 1993). Thus, such kind of religious dogmas continues to perpetuate and reinforce the sheer but hollow need for 'virtuosity' in a woman.

Unshackling the Gender Imbalance

Although there is a legal minimum age at marriage for both men and women, the scales are tilted unfavourably towards girls/ women. Only 4 per cent of Indian boys/ men were married before the age of 18. It was 20 per cent before the age of 21. Contrastingly, 27 per cent of girls/ women were already married before 18 years of age (Rajagopalan, 2020). Leeson and Suarez (2017) rationalize that son preference drives the crucifixion nail very hard on the young girls. Many times, the unwanted daughters are 'disposed of' through child marriage. Another heinous way of 'disposing of' is female foeticide. They, therefore, caution that merely increasing age at marriage cannot undo the deeply ingrained practice of child marriage. Rather socio-cultural changes, education and economic development can show the way.

Society cannot move forward if half of it is held back. Empowering girls and women and thus building their agency is the most important step in bringing about a positive change in society. However, often there are set notions about empowerment, and how it can be achieved. This can also prove to be impediments to achieving what we truly aspire to, in terms of a gender balance.

With patriarchy as the epicentre, the fault lines that emerge render huge cracks in the gender balance. It continues to play a pivotal role in keeping child marriage rooted in society; inducing different vulnerabilities for the child brides, in terms of a shaken and timid personality. Ghosh (2016) and Warrioba (2018) also add that such patriarchal ideals lead to gendered constructions of societal roles and expectations, which mostly favour men. The major reason for early marriage amongst young girls is thus attributed to the patriarchy driven traditional beliefs and norms which are very rigid and entrenched in society. It hence distorts the notion of equality of all human beings. Fox (1989) also concurs that the patriarchal practices and social relations are geared to ensure that women continue to be subverted by their biological roles of reproduction, child-rearing and other entrenched and biased perceptions about gender identity itself.

Eisentein (1999) further highlights that patriarchy is no doubt gender-biased and hierarchical too. Patriarchal values, attitudes and beliefs continue to infuse colour and vigour to the various opinions and decisions we make in our social, cultural, political and economic lives. It influences our interpersonal relationships, the leaders we revere and prefer, religious beliefs, as well as educational practices. Throughout human history, the reciprocal relationship between men and women has defined their lives and how their

relationship has been interwoven thus by society (as cited in Bahlieda, 2015, p. 16).

The Ordeal of Child Marriage

Macleod (2001) argues that one of the most neglected social problems in India is the untimely and early marriage of the girl child. The prevalence itself is a form of tacit approval, of the practice of child marriage in the country, and is an indication that society refuses to recognize its adverse effects specifically on the child brides and on society at large. He adds that it is worsened by the fact that the adverse impact of such a marriage on the life of a woman is often ignored, remains unexamined, or goes unreported.

As a result of child marriage, the young girls end up missing out on education; thus, losing their career and personality development opportunities. Their childhood is trampled upon; their quality of life is degraded. They are denied opportunities as well as the potential to fully participate in the path to society's progress. This results in suppression of the human rights of these young brides who go on to lead a life of painful deprivation, splintered with traumatising memories of a lost childhood.

Discontinuance of education is a cause as well as a consequence of child marriage. NFHS-4 showed that 28 per cent of women ranging from 15-49 years have no schooling. Parents of these young girls feel that it is best to marry them off early with less dowry and lessen the family burden. Post-marriage, education comes to an abrupt halt as marriage involves shouldering the burden of domesticity, and course motherhood. Dowry harassment in the Indian context is yet another nightmare. Sitlhou (2019) highlights the Government of Assam Report where 1606 women succumbed to death due to dowry during 2006-2018. Domestic violence is also another ordeal that these young brides have to endure owing to the lack of dowry needs being fulfilled or even something as trivial as not knowing to cook.

Women: Always the 'Other'

Ancient texts like the *Manusmriti* have tacitly given leeway to child marriage. It talks about the suitable age of marriage for a girl to be somewhere between 8 to 12 years. It also states that it is alright for a man of 30 years to marry a girl as young as 12 years old. Thus, the practice of child marriage can be likened to cultural and social slavery. This slavery is conditioned by social norms and customs; the roots of which are embodied in the patriarchal social setup, the reason being that these norms continue to be defined by men (Ferguson, 1992). Women are denied any role while defining these norms and social constructs. It is often found that the young brides are

unable to express their feelings and emotions to their spouses. It deprives them of their right to have a happy and fulfilling married life thus affecting their behaviour and personality. Child marriage not only deprives the young brides of the wonders of childhood but pushes them into an unfathomable world of forceful sex and consequent motherhood, much before they can comprehend these complexities. Nour (2009) and Wodon (2015) have also highlighted that early marriage shortens a girl's childhood as it stops their education and quickly transitions them to womanhood. They argue that it also impacts their health adversely.

A girl child is violated of her right to equality on various grounds. Section 5(iii) of the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955, requires that the bridegroom be 21 years and the bride 18 years old at the time of marriage. This is an instance of how the Act itself treats girls differently from boys. After marriage, her education is discontinued; there is a change of residence, and domestic responsibilities engulf her. Hence, gender parity is a far cry.

Simone de Beauvoir had aptly noted, *'One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman'* (Beauvoir, 1953). It depicts a woman's life in our society. From different norms to societal role expectations, the life of a woman is largely defined by society and its people. The basic source of oppression of women, some feminists argue is the social and historical construction of women as the quintessential other or the second sex. Simone had also pointed out that Aristotle himself had defined a female as one that lacks qualities. Thus, a woman is understood not as a being herself but always with men. She is never an autonomous being. Hence, she says, *'He is the Subject, he is the Absolute - she is the Other'* Beauvoir (1953, p. 16).

Child Marriage and the Pandemic

The United Nations cautions that approximately 1.5 million underage girls marry each year in India. The pandemic has just worsened it. Calls from such distressed girls to the Government helplines are reported by the Child Protection Officers. The underlying paranoia is heightened as desperate parents in the wake of the pandemic have been rendered jobless. In the absence of a livelihood, they want to marry off their underage daughters to reduce the family burden. What is even more alarming is that girls as young as even 12 years are also being sought to be married off while the pre-pandemic times recorded a typical age of 16- to 17-year-olds. This scenario looms large not just in India but across the world; especially in those pockets of poverty and economic deprivation. UNICEF reports that South Asia has the highest number of child brides. The pandemic has unfortunately pushed

intervention measures against child marriage to a lower rung as more urgent life-threatening scenarios of health care dominate the world now. What is even more regressive is that these young girls are sought as brides by men who are widowers or those who have special needs (Pathak & Frayer, 2020). The plight of these young girls in the aftermath of marriage is, therefore, of untold miseries.

The Times of India screamed in its headlines, ‘Urban Poverty Pushes Up Child Marriage Cases by 45 per cent over 2019’. This was in the relatively developed state of Tamil Nadu. It was reported that the number of marriages which were stopped in 2019 was 2,209. This shockingly rose to 3,208 in 2020 amidst the pandemic. They cite 4 key reasons namely: a) Poverty and loss of livelihood; b) Safety of girl children; c) Closure of schools, and; d) Low marriage expenses during the lockdown. The last one is a terrible incentive, the brunt of which the girl child has to bear. Teachers discovered the ‘married’ status of the young girls upon seeing the ‘*mangalsutra*’, a customary ornament worn by married women in most parts of India. The report suggests that continuously monitoring all girl children, implementing special schemes for them, reopening of schools, activating village level and ward level child protection committees and appointing a special officer to prevent child marriages at the district level can be a way out (Raman, 2021). Since the pandemic is a new phenomenon that the world has never tackled before, several policy changes will indeed have to be initiated as any kind of social and economic meltdown always hits women and children harder.

A recent UNICEF (2021) study also highlights that over the next decade, up to 10 million more girls across the world will be at risk of becoming child brides due to the pandemic. COVID-19 has affected the everyday lives of these innocent young girls in terms of access to education, and severe upheavals in the economic circumstances of their families and communities. The closure of schools has made education a non-option for these households. The digital divide is also a threat that can deepen the rich and poor further as online education eludes the poor. Kundan Pandey (2020) reports that although wireless technology is on the rise, the digital divide wedge between the rich and the poor has only deepened. The poor either do not have a mobile phone, or do not have the money to keep it active, or do not have electricity to recharge it, or do not know much of the operational functions. He also reports that according to the monthly report of the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) on 29 June 2020, there were over 1,160 million wireless subscribers as of February 2020. At the same

time, he highlights data from the Internet Freedom Foundation. It was reported that urban areas have over 104 internet subscriptions per 100 people. In rural areas, it is just around 27 (Pandey (2020)). This is an instance of the deep digital divide between urban and rural areas. In rural areas, the problem of internet access in terms of speed is also another factor. Merely having a network connection cannot be a game-changer in this regard.

UNICEF also reiterates that the pandemic is raising the risks of child marriage in manifold ways. They have enlisted interruptions in education; economic upheavals; disruptions of welfare programmes and services; pregnancies; and death of a parent. Besides these, socio-contextual factors such as conflicts and forced migration can worsen the perils of child marriage. The pre-COVID projections are that 100 million girls will still become child brides by the turn of the next decade. This is despite the global goal of ending child marriage by 2030 (UNICEF, 2021). What could be the post-COVID scenario can only be unfolded by time. A comparison of NFHS-3 and NFHS-4 had shown a declining trend of child marriage in India. The pandemic seems more likely to undo the achievements.

Conclusions

It is thus underlined that the practice of child marriage negatively affects the personality of a girl child. It seriously impacts the mental, physical, social and biological well-being of a girl. All the discussions above have outlined how every aspect of a girl's life at all points are controlled by someone else and not the girl herself. Her identity itself is defined by the people in the society. Child marriage deprives the girl child to even dare to dream altogether; because society has already defined her life for her. Consequently, the young girl before even getting full control or discovering her own body loses that autonomy. A child bride has to face restrictions on her mobility, participation in social life, and even in decision-making regarding her health. All of these result in the girl seeing her self-worth in a negative light, resulting in lowered self-esteem. This lowered self-esteem has implications for both her overall psychological well-being and personality development.

Despite her confidence being shattered, shorn of happiness, freedom denied, emotionally and physically battered; the young bride is still expected to '*walk the societal norms*'. She is expected to exhibit modesty, self-control, and exuberance at all times. The red colour that is ideally associated with happiness, auspiciousness, and festivities on account of marriage, unfortunately, becomes the most repugnant colour. Child marriage engulfs her with sorrow, anger, depression, frustration and the end of her dreams for

a lifetime. The practice of such a marriage undoubtedly has an unnerving impact on the mental, physical, biological and social well-being of a girl where her identity and personality continue to be defined by the people around her.

It is with many merits therefore to argue that to tackle child marriage efficiently, merely raising the legal age at marriage is but a bubble that can burst easily. In our vast country, marriage registrations rarely take place; especially in the rural areas where the most underage marriages take place. A multipronged approach towards meeting the United Nations goal of complete eradication of child marriage needs to be adopted. Enhanced gender parity, undoing the sex taboo, shared decision making within the household, upholding the significance of education, and continuous push towards implementing welfare programmes can pave the way towards a child marriage free India.

References

1. Abbi, A., Jayakumar, K., Raj, M. R., & Padmanabhan, R. (2013). *Child Marriage in India: An Insight into Law and Policy December 2013*. Red Elephant Foundation. <https://www.ohchr.org/documents/issues/women/wrgs/forcedmarriage/ngo/theredelephantfoundation.pdf>.
2. Abraham, L. (2001). Redrawing the Lakshman Rekha: Gender differences and cultural constructions in youth sexuality in urban India. *South Asia: Journal of South Asian Studies*, 24(s1), 133-156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00856400108723441>.
3. Bahlida, R., (2015). The Democratic Gulag: Patriarchy, Leadership & Education. *Counterpoints*, 488, 15-67. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/i40220240>.
4. Beauvoir, S. (1953). *The Second Sex*. Jonathan Cape.
5. Bhattacharya, A., Camacho, D., Kimberly, L. L., & Lukens, E. P. (2019). Women's experiences and perceptions of depression in India: A metaethnography. *Qualitative health research*, 29(1), 80-95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732318811702>.
6. Brain, J. L., Blake, C. F., Bluebond-Langner, M., Chilungu, S. W., Coelho, V. P., Dömötör, T., Gorer, G., La Fontaine, J. S., Levy, S. B., Loukastos, D. Natarajan, N., Raphael, D., Schlegel, A., Stein H.F., & Wilder, W. D. (1977). Sex, Incest, and Death: Initiation Rites Reconsidered [and Comments and Reply]. *Current Anthropology*, 18(2), 191-208. <https://doi.org/10.1086/201884>.
7. Charlesworth, H., Chinkin, C., & Wright, S. (1991). Feminist approaches to international law. *The American Journal of International Law*, 85(4), 613-645. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2203269>.
8. Chowdhury, J. (2020, March 9). *Why Is Sex Or Sexuality Education In Indian Schools Still A Taboo?* *Feminism in India: Intersectional Feminism – Desi Style!*

- <https://feminisminindia.com/2020/03/09/why-sex-sexuality-education-indian-schools-taboo/>.
9. Christianson, M., Teiler, Å., & Eriksson, C. (2021). “A woman’s honor tumbles down on all of us in the family, but a man’s honor is only his”: young women’s experiences of patriarchal chastity norms. *International journal of qualitative studies on health and well-being*, 16(1), 1862480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482631.2020.1862480>.
 10. Collins, P. H. (1986). Learning from the outsider within: The sociological significance of Black feminist thought. *Social problems*, 33(6), s14-s32. <https://doi.org/10.2307/800672>.
 11. Eisenstein, Z. (1999). Constructing a Theory of Capitalist Patriarchy and Socialist Feminism. *Critical Sociology*, 25(2–3), 196–217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08969205990250020901>.
 12. Feder, G. S., Hutson, M., Ramsay, J., & Taket, A. R. (2006). Women exposed to intimate partner violence: expectations and experiences when they encounter health care professionals: a meta-analysis of qualitative studies. *Archives of internal medicine*, 166(1), 22-37. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.166.1.22>.
 13. Ferguson, M. (1992). Mary Wollstonecraft and the problematic of slavery. *Feminist Review*, 42(1), 82-102. <https://doi.org/10.1057%2Ffr.1992.50>.
 14. Fox, B. J. (1989). The feminist challenge: A reconsideration of social inequality and economic development. In R. Brym & B. Fox. *From culture to power: The sociology of English Canada* (pp. 120-167). Oxford University Press.
 15. Fredrickson, B. L., & Roberts, T. A. (1997). Objectification theory: Toward understanding women's lived experiences and mental health risks. *Psychology of women quarterly*, 21(2), 173-206. <https://doi.org/10.1111%2Fj.1471-6402.1997.tb00108.x>.
 16. Gagnon, J. H. (1965). Sexuality and sexual learning in the child. *Psychiatry*, 28(3), 212-228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.1965.11023429>.
 17. Ghosh, B. (2016). The Institution of Motherhood: A Critical Understanding. In Samita Manna & S. Patra (eds.). *Motherhood—Demystification and Denouement*, (pp.17-29). Levant Books. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312076821_The_Institution_of_Motherhood_A_Critical_Understanding
 18. Hasday, J. (2000). Contest and Consent: A Legal History of Marital Rape. *California Law Review*, 88(5), 1373-1505. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3481263>.
 19. IASSCS Conference 2009 Contested Innocence - Sexual Agency in Public and Private Space Abstract book. (2009). *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 11, S1-S135. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27784452>.
 20. India Today Web Desk. (2016, March 12). *Marital rape in India: 36 countries where marital rape is not a crime*. India Today. <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/gk-current-affairs/story/marital-rape-312955-2016-03-12>.
-

21. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS). (2017). National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4), 2015-16. Indian Institute of Population studies, Mumbai. <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR339/FR339.pdf>.
22. Ismail, S., Shajahan, A., Rao, T. S. S., & Wylie, K. (2015). Adolescent sex education in India: Current perspectives. *Indian journal of psychiatry*, 57(4), 333–337. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5545.171843>.
23. Jejeebhoy, S. J., & Bott, S. (2003). “Non-consensual sexual experiences of young people: A review of the evidence from developing countries”. *South & East Asia Regional Working Paper no. 16*. Population Council, New Delhi. https://knowledgecommons.popcouncil.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1525&context=departments_sbsr-rh.
24. Johnston, J. (1993). The sexual enlightenment of children in the modern cultural context—care or corruption? *Sexual and marital therapy*, 8(1), 53-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02674659308404501>.
25. Kabeer, N. (2005). Gender equality and women's empowerment: A critical analysis of the third millennium development goal 1. *Gender & Development*, 13(1), 13-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552070512331332273>.
26. Kapadia, K.M. (1966). *Marriage and family in India*, Oxford University Press.
27. Kopelman, L. (2016). The Forced Marriage of Minors: A Neglected Form of Child Abuse. *Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*, 44(1), 173-181. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073110516644208>.
28. Larson, J. E. (1993). "Women Understand So Little, They Call My Good Nature 'Deceit'": A Feminist Rethinking of Seduction. *Columbia Law Review*, 93(2), 374-472. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1123051>.
29. Leeson, P., & Suarez, P. (2017). Child Brides. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 144, 40-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2017.10.001>.
30. Luke, N., & Munshi, K. (2011). Women as agents of change: Female income and mobility in India. *Journal of Development Economics*, 94(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2010.01.002>.
31. Macleod, C. (2001). Teenage motherhood and the regulation of mothering in the scientific literature: The South African example. *Feminism & Psychology*, 11(4), 493-510. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959353501011004004>.
32. Mahapatro, M., & Singh, S. P. (2020). Coping strategies of women survivors of domestic violence residing with an abusive partner after registered complaint with the family counseling center at Alwar, India. *Journal of community psychology*, 48(3), 818-833. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.22297>.
33. Makkar, S. (2019). Marital Rape: A Non-criminalized Crime in India. *Harvard Human Rights Journal*. <https://harvardhrj.com/2019/01/marital-rape-a-non-criminalized-crime-in-india/>.
34. Marion, A. (2010). *History of Child Marriage in India*. Terres d'Asie. <https://terredasie.com/english/english-articles/history-of-child-marriage-in-india/>.

35. Marphatia, A. A., Ambale, G. S., & Reid, A. M. (2017). Women's marriage age matters for public health: a review of the broader health and social implications in South Asia. *Frontiers in public health*, 5, 269. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00269>.
36. Mokobocho-Mohlakoana, K. (2008). Motherhood and Sexuality. *Agenda: Empowering Women for Gender Equity*, 22(76), 57-64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10130950.2008.9674933>.
37. Mondal, D., Karmakar, S., & Banerjee, A. (2020, December 9). Women's autonomy and utilization of maternal healthcare in India: Evidence from a recent national survey, *PLOS ONE*, 15(12), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243553>.
38. Niaz, U., & Hassan, S. (2006). Culture and mental health of women in South-East Asia. *World Psychiatry*, 5(2), 118-120. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1525125/pdf/wpa050118.pdf>.
39. Nour, N. M. (2009). Child marriage: a silent health and human rights issue. *Reviews in obstetrics and gynecology*, 2(1), 51-56. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2672998/pdf/RIOG002001_0051.pdf.
40. Osthus, I. S., & Sewpaul, V. (2014). Gender, power and sexuality among youth on the streets of Durban: Socio-economic realities. *International Social Work*, 57(4), 326-337. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0020872814524966>.
41. Pandey, K. (2020, July 16-31). *COVID-19 lockdown highlights India's great digital divide*. DownToEarth. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/news/governance/covid-19-lockdown-highlights-india-s-great-digital-divide-72514>.
42. Pathak, S. & Frayer, L. (2020, November 5). *Child Marriages are up in the pandemic: Here's how India tries to stop them*. npr. <https://www.npr.org/sections/goatsandsoda/2020/11/05/931274119/child-marriages-are-up-in-the-pandemic-heres-how-india-tries-to-stop-them>.
43. Paul, P. (2019). Effects of education and poverty on the prevalence of girl child marriage in India: A district-level analysis. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 100, 16-21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2019.02.033>.
44. Poduska, B. (1992). Money, marriage, and Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 35(6), 756-770. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0002764292035006010>.
45. Prakash, R., Singh, A., Pathak, P. K., & Parasuraman, S. (2011). Early marriage, poor reproductive health status of mother and child well-being in India. *BMJ Sexual & Reproductive Health*, 37(3), 136-145. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/jfprhc-2011-0080>.
46. Psaki, S. (2016). Addressing child marriage and adolescent pregnancy as barriers to gender parity and equality in education. *Prospects*, 46(1), 109-129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-016-9379-0>.

47. Rajagopalan, S. (2020, October 26). The economics of India's high prevalence of child brides. Livemint. <https://www.livemint.com/opinion/online-views/the-economics-of-india-s-high-prevalence-of-child-brides-11603727733091.html>.
48. Raman, A. R. (2021, August 18). Tamil Nadu: Urban poverty pushes up child marriage cases by 45% over 2019. The Times of India. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/tamil-nadu-urban-poverty-pushes-up-child-marriage-cases-by-45-over-2019/articleshow/85417751.cms>.
49. Rosaldo, M. Z. (1974). Woman, culture, and society: A theoretical overview. In M. Z. Rosaldo and L. Lamphere. *Woman, culture, and society* (pp. 17-42). Stanford University Press.
50. Rosenzweig, M. R., & Stark, O. (1989). Consumption smoothing, migration, and marriage: Evidence from rural India. *Journal of political Economy*, 97(4), 905-926. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261633>.
51. Santhya, K.G., Haberland, N. and Singh, A. K. (2006). 'She knew only when the garland was put around her neck': Findings from an exploratory study on early marriage in Rajasthan. Population Council, New Delhi. https://knowledgecommons.popcouncil.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1239&context=dapartments_sbsr-pgy.
52. Sen, S. (2021). Introduction. In Samita Sen and Anindita Ghosh (eds.). *Love, Labor and Law: Early and child marriage in India* (xi-xxxvi). Sage Publications.
53. Shah, P. P. (2011). Girls' education and discursive spaces for empowerment: Perspectives from rural India. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 6(1), 90-106. <https://doi.org/10.2304%2Frcie.2011.6.1.90>.
54. Shawki, N. (2015). Norm-based Advocacy and Social Change: An analysis of advocacy efforts to end child marriage. *Social Alternatives*, 34(4), 57-62. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/INFORMIT.382328381472603>.
55. Sitlhou, M. (2019, May 13). 'Juroon, Joutuk, Streedhan': The hidden reality of dowry in Assam. Guwahati: Eastmojo. <https://www.eastmojo.com/in-depth/2019/05/13/juroon-joutuk-streedhan-the-hidden-reality-of-dowry-in-assam>.
56. Supreme Court of India. (2017). Independent Thought v. Union of India & Anr. Writ Petition (Civil) 382 of 2013 Judgement. https://main.sci.gov.in/supremecourt/2013/17790/17790_2013_Judgement_11-Oct-2017.pdf.
57. Taormina, R. J., & Gao, J. H. (2013). Maslow and the motivation hierarchy: Measuring satisfaction of the needs. *The American journal of psychology*, 126(2), 155-177. <https://doi.org/10.5406/amerjpsyc.126.2.0155>.
58. Temin, M., Levine, R., & Stonesifer, S. (2010). Start with a girl: a new agenda for global health. *Issues in Science and Technology*, 26(3), 33-40. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43315160>.
59. Thapan, M. (2004). Embodiment and identity in contemporary society: Femina and the 'new' Indian woman. *Contributions to Indian Sociology*, 38(3), 411-444. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F006996670403800305>.

60. Travers, E. (2018, August 16). Less talk, more action to address child marriage in emergencies. *Girls Not Brides*. <https://www.girlsnotbrides.org/articles/less-talk-end-child-marriage-conflict/>.
61. UNICEF. (2021). *COVID-19: A threat to progress against child marriage*, UNICEF, New York. <https://data.unicef.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/UNICEF-report--COVID-19--A-threat-to-progress-against-child-marriage-1.pdf>.
62. Warioba, I. (2018). Translation of human rights law according to local context: a solution to child marriage in Africa? *Journal of Law, Society and Development*, 5(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.25159/2520-9515/7076>.
63. WHO. (2012). *Child marriage – a threat to health*. World Health Organisation. <https://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/Life-stages/sexual-and-reproductive-health/news/news/2012/12/child-marriage-a-threat-to-health>.
64. Wichstrom, L. (1999). The emergence of gender difference in depressed mood during adolescence: the role of intensified gender socialization. *Developmental psychology*, 35(1), 232-245. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0012-1649.35.1.232>.
65. Williams, L. (1984). When the Woman Looks. Re-Vision: Essays in Feminist Film Criticism. In Mary Ann Doane, Patricia Mellencamp & Linda Williams (eds.), *American Film Institute Monograph Series* (pp. 88-99). Los Angeles.
66. Wodon, Q. (2015). Child marriage, family law, and religion: An introduction to the fall 2015 issue. *The Review of Faith & International Affairs*, 13(3), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15570274.2015.1075761>.